

Implementation of Strategies to Promote Reading Comprehension in Third- And Fourth-Grade Students at Benito Juárez Elementary School: An Action Research Study

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 31 March 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: María Guadalupe Olivares Omaña</p>	<p>This article presents an educational intervention aimed at improving reading comprehension among third- and fourth-grade students at the “Benito Juárez” elementary school in Almoloya, Cuauhtepac, Hidalgo, through strategies aligned with the principles of the New Mexican School. The study involved 45 students aged between 8 and 10 years, divided into two groups: 20 third-grade students and 25 fourth-grade students.</p> <p>The methodology was divided into four phases: diagnosis, planning, implementation, and evaluation. The Early Warning System (SISAT) was used as an instrument to measure progress in reading comprehension before and after the intervention.</p> <p>Despite existing challenges such as social inequality, difficult economic conditions, and the lack of family support and psychopedagogical diagnoses, the results were positive. The implementation of the teaching strategies achieved significant improvements in the students’ reading performance, also increasing their motivation and participation.</p> <p>This study reaffirms that the implementation of appropriate teaching approaches is essential to strengthen reading comprehension, contributing to better academic development among students.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Reading comprehension, educational intervention, Primary education, Reading strategies, New Mexican School.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

At Benito Juárez Elementary School, a significant gap in reading and writing skills was identified during the 2023–2024 school year based on the results obtained from the SISAT assessment. This diagnosis showed that, at the school level, 31% of the students presented difficulties in reading, 27% in literacy, and 45% in mental calculation, highlighting the urgent need to strengthen teaching and learning processes in the area of language and communication.

In response to this situation, a pedagogical intervention focused on reading comprehension was designed and implemented with the aim of improving students' academic performance, selecting the third- and fourth-grade groups. The activities carried out included teacher-led read-aloud sessions, participation of guest readers in the classroom, reading storybooks with images, debates and guided questions, the traveling backpack, and shared reading.

These strategies proved to be effective, as they promoted the active participation of the educational triangle—parents, teachers, and students—and strengthened the links between school and family.

The results of the intervention show significant progress: a greater number of students reached the expected level of reading comprehension, while the group requiring support was considerably reduced. Before the intervention, only 22% of the students were at the expected level, while 45% were in development and 33% required intensive support. After the systematic application of the reading strategies, most students showed notable progress in the comprehension and analysis of texts, confirming the effectiveness of the implemented approach.

In this regard, the experience developed at Benito Juárez Elementary School demonstrates that the intentional planning of reading activities, together with collaboration between school and family, can positively transform the learning process. Strengthening reading comprehension from the early

years of education not only improves academic performance, but also promotes critical thinking, effective communication, and a love for reading as a cultural, social, and transformative practice, in line with the principles of the New Mexican School.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Contemporary education is conceived as an essential pillar in the generation and distribution of knowledge; however, for this process to be meaningful, it is necessary to understand the ways in which students construct knowledge. In this context, reading comprehension emerges as a central component of learning, as it is essential for students to interpret, reflect on, and assimilate the information they read.

According to the 2022 Curriculum of the New Mexican School (NEM), reading comprehension represents a fundamental challenge for developing critical, analytical, and reflective thinking. This approach recognizes that reading goes beyond the Languages learning field, also impacting the areas of Knowledge and Scientific Thinking, Ethics, Nature and Societies, and Human and Community Development. Reading, as a social and emancipatory practice, allows students to understand their environment, build collective meanings, and transform reality through dialogue and reflection [1].

In theoretical terms, reading comprehension is understood as an active process of constructing meaning through the interaction between the reader, the text, and the context. Various authors agree that reading involves both extracting and constructing meaning. Snow (2001) defines it as a simultaneous process of extracting and constructing meaning through interaction with written language [2].

Similarly, Johnston (1989) and Díaz-Barriga and Hernández (2001) argue that reading comprehension is a constructive and strategic activity in which the reader relates new information to prior knowledge, activating mental schemas that allow the interpretation and understanding of the text [3].

Authors such as Solé (1992) emphasize the importance of reading strategies such as inference and prediction that readers use before, during, and after reading to plan, monitor, and evaluate their comprehension [4]. For their part, Vygotsky and Bruner highlight the social and cognitive nature of learning, recognizing that comprehension develops through interaction and the use of language as a means of constructing shared knowledge [5].

These levels are interrelated and allow a gradual progression toward deep and meaningful reading. According to Catalá et al. (2001) and Pinzas (2007), mastery of the literal and inferential levels forms the basis for achieving critical comprehension, understood as the ability to analyze, compare, and make well-founded judgments about what has been read [6,7].

In the Mexican educational context, assessment tools such as PISA, PLANEA, SISAT, and MEJOREDUC provide valuable information about achievement levels in reading comprehension. These assessments make it possible to identify the extent to which students extract information, interpret, analyze textual structures, and reflect on language, while also providing teachers with diagnostic data to plan appropriate pedagogical interventions and prevent educational lag.

Finally, theories of deep processing and theories of reading comprehension—linear, interactive, transactional, and literary—provide complementary frameworks for understanding how students construct meaning. While the linear theory considers comprehension as the reproduction of the text, the interactive and transactional theories conceive it as a dynamic process of exchange between the reader and the text, where meaning is constructed and shared. The literary theory, for its part, emphasizes the aesthetic, emotional, and reflective dimension of reading.

Overall, this theoretical framework supports the idea that reading comprehension is a cognitive, social, and cultural process that is essential for meaningful learning and the holistic development of students. Developing it from the early years of schooling, in accordance with the principles of the New Mexican School, is an essential condition for strengthening critical thinking and promoting an equitable, humanistic, and transformative education.

III. METHODOLOGY

The present work corresponds to an **action research study**, whose purpose is to improve the reading comprehension skills of primary school students through the application of didactic strategies. This approach was carried out in four main phases: an initial diagnosis, planning of the design, implementation of a pedagogical intervention, and finally the evaluation of the results obtained (Hernández & Mendoza, 2023) [8].

Determination of the Population and Sample

The population under study consisted of the educational community of the “Benito Juárez” Elementary School, specifically the third- and fourth-grade groups. The sample was census-based and included a total of 45 students, distributed as follows.

Third grade: 20 students (9 girls and 11 boys) aged between 8 and 9 years.

Fourth grade: 25 students (15 girls and 10 boys) aged between 9 and 10 years.

The selection of these groups was based on the fact that the students are in **phase four** of the reading process (NEM), in which they deepen the acquisition of reading and develop **independent reading skills** (Secretaría de Educación Pública [SEP], 2024) [1].

Data Collection Technique and Instrument

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Diagnosis: It was based on the identification of students who are in phase four of the reading process (NEM) and who have not yet developed autonomous reading skills, or who show difficulties in different aspects of reading. This was carried out through the use of the SISAT test (Early Warning System) to determine the students’ reading levels [9].

Planning: Design and implementation of the strategy, collection of materials, and improvement of the space to promote the enjoyment of reading.

Intervention: The educational intervention was carried out through the implementation of didactic strategies focused on strengthening reading comprehension. These strategies included the systematic development of reading activities both in the classroom and at home, promoting the active participation of the students.

In the school context, the readings were guided by the classroom teacher, who supported the students in the application of reading comprehension techniques before, during, and after reading.

Additionally, reading at home was encouraged with the support of family members, in order to reinforce learning and promote the continuity of the educational process outside the classroom.

To ensure the proper implementation of the intervention, clear information and specific materials were provided to both teachers and families, which were aimed at developing activities designed to strengthen reading comprehension skills.

These actions sought to create a collaborative environment between the school and the home, contributing to the improvement of the students’ reading performance

Evaluation: At the end of the pedagogical intervention, the SISAT test was applied in order to evaluate the progress achieved by the students and to analyze the impact of the implemented didactic strategies. The results obtained made it possible to assess the level of improvement in the evaluated skills and to compare the diagnostic results with those obtained after the intervention

Table 1. Results of the Evaluation Before the Implementation (SISAT, 2024)

According to the results of the initial reading comprehension diagnosis, 26.7% of the students were placed in the needs support level, as they show poor reading comprehension, as well as insecurity or indifference toward reading. 24.4% were at the developing level, indicating that these students have a partial understanding of the text and limited confidence when reading. Finally, 48.9% reached the expected level, demonstrating a general understanding of reading.

These results were obtained from a total sample of 45 third- and fourth-grade students from Benito Juárez Elementary School.

Table 2. Evaluation results after the implementation (SISAT, 2024).

Based on the reading comprehension graph after the intervention and considering a total sample of 45 students.

The results obtained after the intervention show a significant improvement in reading comprehension levels. 75.6% (34) of the students reached the expected level, while 17.8% (8) were at the developing level, and only 6.7% (3) required additional support. These data reflect a favorable impact of the implemented strategies, considerably reducing the percentage of students at risk and increasing the level of academic achievement

V. DISCUSSION

The results obtained show that the implementation of strategies aimed at strengthening reading comprehension had a positive impact on students’ performance. In the initial diagnosis, 26.7% of the students were at the requires support level and 48.9% were at the expected level. After the intervention, the percentage of students at the expected level increased to 75.6%, while the group that required support decreased to 6.7%.

These results indicate that the strategies applied, based on guided reading in the classroom, family support, and the use of specific instructional materials, promoted the development of reading skills. The improvement observed is consistent with studies that highlight the importance of

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systematic and contextualized intervention to increase performance in reading comprehension in primary education.

Likewise, collaborative work between teachers and families may have significantly influenced the progress, by reinforcing reading processes both inside and outside the classroom.

However, the study presents some limitations, such as the limited time of implementation and the absence of a control group that would allow for more precise comparisons.

In conclusion, the findings suggest that the application of structured and contextualized strategies contributes significantly to the strengthening of reading comprehension; therefore, their continuation and adaptation in other school groups is recommended

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The activities implemented proved to be effective instructional strategies that strengthened the participation of the educational triangle—parents, teachers, and students—consolidating collaborative work in favor of the development of reading comprehension. Reading, understood as an essential means for integral development, and reading comprehension as a tool for interpreting the social environment, not only contributed to improving academic performance but also gave new meaning to learning and to the interpretation of information.

It was confirmed that reading comprehension is constructed through the interaction between the reader’s prior knowledge and the textual content, mobilizing various cognitive skills that allow the development of a coherent representation of ideas. This process requires intentional pedagogical guidance to fully develop communicative competencies and critical thinking skills.

However, it was also evident that there is still a lack of attention to the promotion of reading comprehension in primary education, where reading fluency is often prioritized over the interpretation of meaning. In this regard, it is recommended to organize workshops for parents to raise awareness about the importance of promoting reading at home, as well as teacher training in metacognitive strategies that strengthen the reading process and promote deeper and more meaningful comprehension.

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